

Purple Sweet Potato Pancake Intervention on Blood Glucose Control in Type 2 Diabetes Patients

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes Mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels due to impaired insulin production or function. Nutritional therapy plays a critical role in managing Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), particularly through the consumption of foods with a *Low Glycemic Index* to prevent sudden spikes in blood glucose. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of purple sweet potato rolled pancake consumption on blood glucose levels in individuals with T2DM. A case study was conducted in April 2025 at Blambangan Hospital Banyuwangi, involving outpatient observation over a one-week period. Data collected included dietary intake, clinical symptoms, anthropometric measurements, and biochemical parameters. This result is a following the nutritional intervention, patients experienced a reduction in physical complaints, an improvement in dietary intake, and a gradual decrease in blood glucose levels, although the levels had not yet reached target values. The findings suggest that incorporating purple sweet potato rolled pancakes as part of a dietary intervention may contribute to improved blood glucose control and general clinical condition in patients with T2DM. Continuous monitoring and longer intervention periods may be necessary to achieve optimal glycemic targets.

KEYWORDS: blood glucose control, purple sweet potato, low glycemic index, type 2 diabetes mellitus, nutritional intervention

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I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a serious, chronic disease that occurs when the pancreas fails to produce enough insulin [1]. According to the 2018 Basic Health Research data, the prevalence of diabetes mellitus based on diagnosis in Indonesia at the age of ≥ 15 years was 2%. This figure is higher than the prevalence of diabetes in the 2013 Basic Health Research, which was 1.5%. Risk factors for type 2 diabetes mellitus include age, gender, unhealthy diet, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, and infection of the pancreatic gland [2].

Diabetes mellitus has symptoms namely polyuria, polydipsia, polyphagia and weight loss without a clear cause, while the non-specific symptoms of Diabetes Mellitus include weakness, tingling, wounds that are difficult to heal, itching, blurred eyes, erectile dysfunction in

men and vulvar pruritus in women. Diabetes Mellitus can be diagnosed with three diagnostic criteria, namely the presence of typical symptoms of Diabetes Mellitus, Random Blood Glucose (RBG) ≥ 200 mg/dL or Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG) ≥ 126 mg/dL, 2-hour plasma glucose at TTGO ≥ 200 mg/dL and HbA1c examination $\geq 16,5\%$ [3].

Diabetes Mellitus can cause various complications of increasing disease due to blockage of blood vessels both microvascular such as retinopathy, nephropathy and macrovascular such as coronary artery disease and also lower limb blood vessels [4]. One of the important things for people with Diabetes Mellitus is blood glucose control. Controlling blood glucose levels in patients with Diabetes Mellitus is related to dietary factors or food planning,

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because nutrition has a close relationship with Diabetes Mellitus [5].

Nutritional therapy is provided by applying the principle of food ingredients that contain *Low Glycemic Index*, so that when consumed it will not raise blood glucose drastically. Purple sweet potato is one type of tuber that has low glycemic index so that it does not increase blood significantly and also because it has antioxidant activity.

The antioxidant activity of purple sweet potato is due to the presence of anthocyanins which have greater antioxidant ability than other phenolic compounds in purple sweet potato. The anthocyanin compound content of purple sweet potato is 0,4-0,6 mg anthocyanin/g which has the ability as an antidiabetic, which can reduce blood sugar, inhibit free radical production, increase insulin secretion, and prevent insulin resistance [5]

According to Sutrisno [5], purple sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* poiret) is a good source of carbohydrates and also acts as a source of dietary fiber and a source of beta carotene. Contains carbohydrates, protein, fat, calcium, phosphorus, iron, vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin B1 and anthocyanin pigments which are higher than other varieties. Carbohydrates contained in purple sweet potatoes are included in the *Low Glycemic Index* so that when consumed, they will not raise blood glucose drastically.

Home visits allow long-term nutritional maintenance which can further assist patients in regulating their daily diet, and improve quality of life. The purpose of this study was to determine the provision of purple sweet potato rolled pancake on the control of blood glucose levels in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

II. METHOD

The Case study was conducted in April 2025 in outpatients of Blambangan Banyuwangi Hospital. The method used for data collection is observation 3 times for 1 week in the intake domain with the comstock method, the physical domain with interviews, the anthropometric domain with weight measurement, and the biochemical domain by looking at RBG results. The intervention was carried out by giving purple sweet potato rolled pancakes with a weight per fruit @ 50 grams for 1 week (1 day given 2 rolled pancakes). The target achievement in the intake aspect is the fulfillment of intake by $\geq 80\%$ and in the biochemical aspect of RBG < 200 mg/dL [6].

III. DISCUSSION

In this case study, a 52-year-old female patient was admitted to the Internal Medicine treatment unit for 4 days. During the treatment, the patient had complaints of decreased appetite so that he was only able to consume food $< 60\%$ of the needs. And from the results of laboratory tests obtained RBG result of 243 mg/dL. The food consumed was team rice, animal side dishes, vegetable side dishes, vegetables and interludes in the forms of biscuits, milk and

fruit. The patient's food tolerance improved every day until the patient could consume almost 80% of the needs at the time of discharge.

The patient's condition improved every day and he claimed that nausea decreased, appetite increased every day. On discharge, the patient was instructed to consume 1500 kcal and 246 grams of carbohydrates, preferably complex carbohydrates and *Low Glycemic Index*. The dietitian also explained how further home care visits for nutritional therapy would be an opportunity to improve the patient's knowledge and skills in the form of recommended meal selection and good food processing.

IV. INTERVENTIONS AND RESULT

The first visit with the patient was conducted after their discharge from the hospital. During the observation, the patient still appeared weak, experienced slight nausea, and had inadequate food intake. The patient's most recent Random Blood Glucose (RBG) result was 195 mg/dL. Education was provided on how to prepare snacks that can help control blood glucose levels.

The snack formulation was created by taking into account the patient's eating habits and the availability of food ingredients at their home. Both the patient and their family received education on how to prepare the snack as an interlude meal. The recommended snack was a rolled pancake made from purple sweet potato, filled with apple and cinnamon. Both purple sweet potato and apple have a *Low Glycemic Index*, making them suitable components for a diabetes friendly snack.

In addition, these ingredients are rich in antioxidants and dietary fiber. Besides being highly nutritious, this snack is also low in calories, helping to stabilize blood sugar without causing spikes. The preparation method does not involve frying, thus avoiding excess fat intake, which is particularly beneficial for diabetic patients. During the first visit, the patient was only able to consume one rolled pancake due to nausea and reduced appetite.

The second home visit was conducted three days later. The patient appeared more energetic and reported an improved appetite with reduced nausea. Daily food intake had increased compared to the first visit, reaching approximately 1300 kcal, 45 grams of protein, 28 grams of fat, and 202 grams of carbohydrates. The meals consisted of rice, boiled chicken or eggs, vegetables, and tempeh. As a snack, the patient consumed two pieces of the purple sweet potato rolled pancake, which were well accepted. A blood glucose check using the Easy Touch GCHb device showed an RBG level of 173 mg/dL. Although this was still above the normal range, there was a notable decrease from the previous measurement.

The third home visit was conducted on day seven. The patient appeared more active and was willing to do household chores and walk around the house. The patient reported improved appetite, no nausea, and better sleep

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quality. The snack was consistently consumed, and the RBG level had further decreased to 155 mg/dL. Although still above the normal range, the continued reduction in blood sugar levels indicated progress, likely due to the patient's improved condition and adherence to the diet recommended by the Dietitian.

Overall, the patient showed significant improvements in food intake, physical condition, and biochemical parameters. Following the third home visit, a follow-up call confirmed that the patient continued to eat well and met the dietary targets set by the Dietitian.

Figure 1. Patient's energy consumption in three home visits

Figure 2. Carbohydrate consumption of the patient in three home visits

V. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Based on the results of monitoring and evaluation, the patient's energy intake increased to 73% of the recommended requirement during the first visit. A diet was provided that was adjusted to the patient's condition. At the second visit, the energy intake reached 1300 kcal, and during the third visit, it increased again to 1425 kcal.

Anthropometric monitoring and evaluation were conducted by measuring body weight. The results showed a decrease in the patient's weight. This indicates that the dietary intervention aimed at achieving an ideal body weight was effective, although the target has not yet been fully reached.

Monitoring and evaluation of snack intake revealed that during the first visit, the patient was only able to consume one piece of the rolled pancake snack due to ongoing nausea. However, by the second and third visits, intake

increased, with the patient able to consume the recommended two pieces, as the symptoms had subsided.

In addition to dietary intake, biochemical monitoring was also conducted using a blood glucose meter. It was found that the patient's random blood glucose (RBG) level decreased by 22 mg/dL at the second visit, and by an additional 18 mg/dL at the third visit. This reduction was influenced not only by pharmacological therapy but also by the inclusion of purple sweet potato rolled pancake snacks in the diet. Furthermore, the patient demonstrated good compliance with the prescribed diet by avoiding foods high in simple carbohydrates and calories.

During the home visits, the patient's family shared that she lives with her husband and one child. She works as a vegetable vendor. The patient's house is located close to the market, which facilitates easy access to a variety of food items.

Table 1. Major Diseases Causing Death in Hospital Monitoring and Evaluation Antropometry, Intake Analysis, Dietary Formula and Biochemistry

	First Visit	Second Visit	Third Visit
Antropometry			
Height	162 cm	-	-
Weight	84 kg	83	83,8
%LiLA	112%		
Intake analysis			
	Energy 1173 kcal	Energy 1300 kcal	Energy 1425 kcal
Snack Formula (Modified Diet)	1 pieces (50 gr/fruit)	2 pieces (50 gr/fruit)	2 pieces (50 gr/fruit)
Random Glucose	Bloc 195 mg/dL	173 mg/dL	155 mg/dL

A. Nutrient Content

Nutrients that are particularly important for patients with diabetes mellitus include carbohydrates and fibre. Carbohydrates not only serve as the main source of energy, but also help prevent excessive protein breakdown and support fat and mineral metabolism.

Dietary fiber plays a significant role in regulating blood sugar levels. It can slow the movement of food through the digestive tract and inhibit enzyme activity, resulting in slower digestion and a more gradual rise in blood glucose levels. The recommended daily fiber intake for individuals with diabetes mellitus is 20–35 grams per day, with water-soluble fibre being the priority due to its greater effect on glycaemic control [7].

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Table 2. Nutrient content of purple sweet potato rolled pancakes/portion

Energy and Nutrient Content	Purple Sweet Potato Rolled Pancake
Energy (kcal)	141,3
Protein (g)	2,8
Fat (g)	2,6
Carbohydrate (g)	27,5
fiber (g)	21

VI. SUMMARY OF PATIENT PATIENT PROGRESS

The diet provided was adjusted to meet the nutritional needs of patients with Diabetes Mellitus, based on Perkeni guidelines. According to these guidelines, energy intake is set at 25 kcal/kg of ideal body weight (IBW), with protein comprising 15–20% of total caloric intake, fat 20–35%, and carbohydrates 45–65% of total energy. Nutritional calculations followed the Perkeni formula, taking into consideration stress factors, activity level, age, and body weight adjustments [7].

During hospitalization, the patient was unable to meet nutritional targets due to reduced appetite. However, food intake gradually improved during the treatment period. This progress was largely supported by the family's cooperation in implementing dietary recommendations and providing emotional motivation to the patient.

As a result, home visits became an effective strategy to educate the patient on how to achieve targeted energy, carbohydrate, and other macronutrient intake, along with understanding their health benefits.

Home visits also had a positive psychological impact on the patient. While in the hospital, the patient appeared unmotivated and less engaged. However, during home visits, the patient showed increased enthusiasm, as the setting allowed both the patient and family members to ask questions and receive clear, personalized explanations. These visits also provided practical education on how to select and prepare appropriate food ingredients.

The patient appeared happier and more motivated during the second and third visits. The physical improvements observed and experienced by the patient contributed to a sense of calm and optimism, reinforcing the belief that nutritional interventions could indeed make a meaningful difference in their recovery.

Overall, the home visits received good feedback from the patient and his family. They were grateful for the guidance on diabetic intermittent feeding and gained knowledge on the benefits of nutrition and physical activity.

Table 3. Summary of patient progress

	First visit	Second visit	Third visit
Physical	Fully conscious	Fully conscious	Fully conscious
Clinical	Patient feels nauseous and appears weak	The patient lo energized, nausea reduce	Lively, energetic, and able to do homework and sunbathe regularly
Food tolerance assessment	nausea, decreased appetite, thirsty easily	Appetite increased, nausea reduced	Appetite increased, no nausea

Blood glucose levels in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus decreased following the consumption of purple sweet potato rolled pancakes. This suggests that incorporating purple sweet potato into a diabetes specific diet can support better glycemic control.

Diet therapy for diabetes mellitus can benefit from the inclusion of purple sweet potato, helping to regulate blood glucose levels and potentially prevent further complications associated with uncontrolled diabetes.

VII. RECOMMENDATION

There are certain limitations, such as difficulties in providing comprehensive care for patients at home due to the lack of involvement from other essential medical professionals. Additionally, individuals with specialized skills in preparing diabetes-friendly meals are needed to ensure proper dietary management.

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